

Efficiency and Productivity Analysis of Indian State Road Transport Undertakings

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Abstract

Purpose - This study aims to assess the technical efficiency and productivity changes of significant Indian State Road Transport Undertakings (SRTUs) between 2019 and 2021.

Design/Methodology/Approach - This study is based on a quantitative method. Data has been analysed through Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) using the CCR model and the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI). Fleet Held and Total Cost are inputs; Revenue-Earning Kilometres and Passengers Carried are outputs.

Findings - The findings show that administrators such as Gujarat SRTC, PEPSU RTC, and Tripura RTC had excellent pre-pandemic efficiency, but COVID-19 disruptions caused widespread declines in 2020. While Maharashtra SRTC and high-cost operators like Delhi TC continued to suffer from inefficiency, Telangana SRTC and Andhra Pradesh SRTC experienced robust MPI growth in 2021. Operational findings are supported by financial data, which demonstrates higher losses. The analysis highlights scale inefficiencies and the necessity of focused improvements.

Practical implications - DEA, MPI and Financial ratios can be used by policy administrators or managers to improve the service quality of public transport.

Keywords: *Data Envelopment Analysis, Financial Performance, Malmquist Productivity Index, State Road Transport Undertakings, Technical Efficiency, COVID-19*

1. Introduction

The transportation industry is an essential part of the country's economic growth, and road transportation, especially through State Transport Undertakings (STUs), is essential for linking rural and remote regions (Pal & Mitra, 2016). State-run STUs play important societal responsibilities by offering affordable passenger transport across India. Since STU is a public service, it is essential to continuously assess its performance, including its internal output efficiency, fare regulations, and investment requirements. It is more difficult to determine precisely what resources are needed to provide services in the passenger transport industry than in manufacturing, where cost-accounting techniques may readily detect inefficiencies, making efficiency measurement in this sector more difficult.

DEA, or data envelopment analysis, a non-parametric, linear programming-based methodology, was first proposed by Farrell in 1957 and expanded upon by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes in 1978. It was first applied to assess and contrast the effectiveness of nonprofit organisations whose operations cannot be quantified by revenue. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), which measures "technical efficiency," is frequently used by researchers to address issues (Agarwal et al., 2010). Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a widely used research technique, especially in efficiency analysis. It manages multiple inputs and outputs simultaneously, provides benchmarks, and sets improvement goals. A Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) evaluates the relative efficacy of a collection of homogenous decision-making units by dividing the weighted total of inputs by the weighted sum of outputs (Kumar, 2011); (Saxena & Saxena, 2010).

Another important instrument for productivity and efficiency study is the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI), which tracks changes in total factor productivity (TFP) over time for decision-making units (DMUs), such as businesses, industries, or nations (Caves et al., 1982). The index is based on concepts proposed by Sten Malmquist (1953) regarding distance function-based quantity indices in a customer context.

Fare et al. (1994) divided it into two primary parts (Lovell, 2003):

- a. Efficiency Change (Catch-up):** Calculates the technical efficiency change, or how much a DMU approaches the frontier.
- b. Technical Change (Frontier Shift):** Indicates how innovation or technological advancement has changed the production frontier itself.

2. Literature Review

State Transport Undertakings (STUs), which are publicly owned and have a history of financial problems, operate the majority of the bus transport industry in India. However, these losses are not intrinsically negative, as STUs target social purposes rather than pure profit. Therefore, efficiency and effectiveness are more important than profitability alone for publicly owned companies (Singh & Jha, 2017).

Efficiency evaluation is a crucial managerial tool for determining how well resources are being used to produce the intended results. For this assessment, the different methods can be parametric or econometric employing a well productivity function that is either non-parametric or defined through the use of data envelopment analysis (Saxena & Saxena, 2010); (Nagadevara, 2008); (Paradi & Zhu, 2013). To evaluate and improve the efficacy of state-run passenger road transport services, regular efficiency evaluation is essential, particularly through Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) (Zizka, 2017); (Shrivastava & Saxena Neeta, 2015); (Saxena & Kapoor, 2015); (Praveen Kumar et al., 2023); (Zehmed & Jawab, 2020).

By using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) technique with our input and output variables, the technical efficiency of the STUs is assessed (Bhagavath, 2006); (Paradi et al., 2011). Fleet size, Total staff, Fuel consumption and Accident per lakh kilometres are taken as inputs and Bus utilisation, Passenger kilometres and Load factor are taken as outputs. (Agarwal et al., 2010). The CCR, BCC, and Andersen and Petersen's super-efficiency models are three well-known data envelopment analysis (DEA) models that have been used to calculate different efficiency scores for distinct SRTUs (Kumar, 2011); (Saxena, 2019). Over 10,000 journal papers covering the first 40 years of scholarly literature in DEA (1978–2016) were surveyed and analysed by (Emrouznejad & Yang, 2018). Their work demonstrates how DEA research is growing quickly, with notable increases in both methodological developments and practical applications (Gadepalli & Rayaprolu, 2020).

In Index Numbers: Essays in Honour of Sten Malmquist, Fare, Grosskopf, and Roos (1998) provide a thorough analysis of the theory and application of Malmquist Productivity Indexes (MPI). They examined theoretical extensions, decompositions, and early implementations, emphasising the benefits of the index in capturing advancements in technology and efficiency (Johnes, 2006); (Lee et al., n.d.). Robust, fuzzy, interval, and stochastic versions of the MPI have been developed as a result of data uncertainty. (Peykani et al., 2025) integrated robust optimisation with envelopment and multiplier forms to present a robust MPI framework under deep uncertainty. Other studies deal with ambiguous data, such as COVID-19 healthcare assessments (Peykani et al., 2025). Banking, healthcare, higher education, agriculture, transportation, energy, and manufacturing are some of the industries that have used the DEA and MPI (Johnes, 2006). Because of its flexibility and decomposability, and non-parametric nature, the MPI and DEA is still a fundamental component in modern productivity analysis (Pourmahmoud & Bagheri, 2023); (Shojaie et al., 2024); (Yang & Soltani, 2021); (Kerstens et al., 2022).

3. Research Methodology

Data Sources	Financial and operational information from the official website that is consistent with MoRTH reports
DEA Model	Input-oriented CCR (Constant Returns to Scale) model. Inputs: Fleet Held, Total Cost. Outputs: Revenue Earning Km, Passengers Carried. Full efficiency is indicated by an efficiency score of 1. Slacks evaluates possible enhancements
Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI)	It breaks down changes in productivity into changes in efficiency and technical advancements between the years 2019–2020 and 2020–2021. MPI greater than 1 is a sign of growth
Financial Analysis	Operating Ratio = (Total Cost / Total Revenue) × 100; Net Profit/Loss; ratios like Revenue/KM, Cost/KM
Software Used	Python

Research Objectives:

1. To evaluate the technical efficiency using the CCR Model of Data Envelopment Analysis of 25 major Indian State Road Transport Undertakings for 2019-2021.
2. To assess how SRTU productivity changed between 2019–2020 and 2020–2021 using the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI).
3. To evaluate SRTUs' financial performance using important measures like Operating Ratio, Revenue per KM, Cost per KM, and Net Profit/Loss.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The efficiency, productivity, and financial performance of 25 major Indian State Road Transport Undertakings (SRTUs) for the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 are thoroughly examined in this section. With Fleet Held and Total Cost as inputs and Revenue Earning Kilometres and Passengers Carried as outputs, the analysis is based on the input-oriented CCR (Charnes-Cooper-Rhodes) model under Constant Returns to Scale. The Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI) and comprehensive financial statistics support the findings. Every three years, all 25 SRTUs are highlighted.

4.1 DEA Efficiency Scores and Slacks Analysis- CCR Model

Table 4.1.1: DEA Efficiency Scores, Input/Output Slacks and Interpretation- 2019

SRTU	Efficiency Score	Efficient	Input Slacks (Fleet, Cost)	Output Slacks (Rev KM, Passengers)	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	1.0000	Yes	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
Maharashtra SRTC	0.7135	No	(0, 0)	(0, 1620.97)	Inefficient (Shortfall of passengers)
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.8775	No	(0, 558)	(0, 0)	Inefficient (Additional cost)
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.9169	No	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Highly Efficient
Telangana SRTC	0.8463	No	(0, 411.35)	(0, 0)	Inefficient (Additional cost)
Karnataka SRTC	0.9564	No	(0, 518.03)	(0, 1645.16)	Near Efficient
North Western Karnataka RTC	0.8756	No	(0, 35.02)	(0, 387.1)	Inefficient
Rajasthan SRTC	0.8468	No	(0, 93.15)	(0, 322.58)	Inefficient
Kerala SRTC	0.8337	No	(0, 447.17)	(0, 1096.77)	Inefficient
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	0.8822	No	(0, 45.58)	(0, 367.74)	Inefficient
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	0.9393	No	(0, 181.59)	(0, 935.48)	Near Efficient

Delhi TC	0.9740	No	(0, 5231.96)	(0, 0)	Highly Efficient (high cost slack)
Himachal RTC	0.7937	No	(0, 0)	(0, 505.32)	Inefficient (Shortfall of passengers)
Uttarakhand TC	0.9044	No	(0, 0)	(0, 122.26)	Inefficient
PEPSU RTC	1.0000	Yes	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
North Bengal STC	0.9032	No	(0, 18.06)	(0, 119.35)	Inefficient
South Bengal STC	0.8873	No	(0, 0)	(0, 82.47)	Inefficient
Odisha SRTC	0.9401	No	(0, 72.07)	(0, 161.29)	Near Efficient
West Bengal Transport Corp.	0.8964	No	(0, 50.05)	(0, 58.06)	Inefficient
Assam STC	0.9239	No	(0, 0)	(0, 131.76)	Inefficient
Bihar SRTC	0.9359	No	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Highly Efficient
J&K SRTC	0.8899	No	(0, 0)	(0, 188.81)	Inefficient
Meghalaya STC	0.9462	No	(0, 7.1)	(0, 79.03)	Near Efficient
Tripura RTC	1.0000	Yes	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient

Table 4.1.2: DEA Efficiency Scores, Input/Output Slacks and Interpretation- 2020

SRTU	Efficiency Score	Input Slacks (Fleet, Cost)	Output Slacks (Rev KM, Passengers)	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
Maharashtra SRTC	0.5957	(0, 261.31)	(0, 1230.77)	Very Inefficient
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.7000	(0, 655.17)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
Telangana SRTC	0.6443	(0, 531.5)	(0, 0)	Very Inefficient
Karnataka SRTC	0.8230	(0, 735.13)	(0, 1153.85)	Inefficient
North Western Karnataka RTC	0.8504	(0, 337.29)	(0, 46.15)	Inefficient
Rajasthan SRTC	0.8150	(0, 414.46)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Kerala SRTC	0.7115	(0, 1058.58)	(0, 769.23)	Inefficient
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	0.8572	(0, 346.01)	(0, 15.38)	Inefficient
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	0.8011	(0, 520.2)	(0, 38.46)	Inefficient
Delhi TC	0.7320	(0, 4982.43)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Himachal RTC	0.7590	(0, 171.79)	(0, 53.85)	Inefficient
Uttarakhand TC	0.8964	(0, 188.62)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
PEPSU RTC	0.9824	(0, 227.65)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
North Bengal STC	0.8692	(0, 129.09)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
South Bengal STC	0.8674	(0, 123.46)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Odisha SRTC	0.8705	(0, 275.94)	(0, 0)	Inefficient

West Bengal Transport Corp.	0.8679	(0, 145.84)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Assam STC	0.8652	(0, 135.55)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Bihar SRTC	0.9015	(0, 76.6)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
J&K SRTC	0.8457	(0, 125.14)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Meghalaya STC	0.9269	(0, 56.71)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
Tripura RTC	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient

Table 4.1.3: DEA Efficiency Scores, Input/Output Slacks and Interpretation- 2021

SRTU	Efficiency Score	Input Slacks (Fleet, Cost)	Output Slacks (Rev KM, Passengers)	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	0.9327	(0, 0)	(3148.9, 0)	Near Efficient (Shortfall of revenue)
Maharashtra SRTC	0.6185	(0, 719.08)	(0, 2058.82)	Very Inefficient
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.9582	(1134.02, 0)	(1400, 0)	Near Efficient
Telangana SRTC	0.9774	(0, 0)	(666.88, 0)	Highly Efficient
Karnataka SRTC	0.8824	(0, 1297.06)	(0, 941.18)	Inefficient
North Western Karnataka RTC	0.8081	(0, 182.05)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Rajasthan SRTC	0.8305	(0, 406.04)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Kerala SRTC	0.8403	(0, 1549.16)	(0, 529.41)	Inefficient
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	0.8302	(0, 177.97)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	0.8850	(0, 823.78)	(0, 352.94)	Inefficient
Delhi TC	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
Himachal RTC	0.7924	(0, 238.38)	(0, 317.65)	Inefficient
Uttarakhand TC	0.9219	(0, 149.9)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
PEPSU RTC	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient
North Bengal STC	0.9207	(0, 158.44)	(0, 5.88)	Near Efficient
South Bengal STC	0.9123	(0, 97.38)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
Odisha SRTC	0.9284	(0, 278)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
West Bengal Transport Corp.	0.8963	(0, 124.89)	(0, 0)	Inefficient
Assam STC	0.9290	(0, 162.97)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
Bihar SRTC	0.9294	(0, 6.07)	(0, 0)	Near Efficient
J&K SRTC	0.8969	(0, 160.69)	(0, 76.47)	Inefficient
Meghalaya STC	0.9580	(0, 60.83)	(0, 18.24)	Highly Efficient
Tripura RTC	1.0000	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	Fully Efficient

4.2 Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI) Analysis

The Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI) calculates the difference in total factor productivity between two periods. It divides changes in production into changes in technical efficiency and technological advancement and is calculated using DEA. An MPI number greater than 1 indicates productivity growth, a value equal to 1

indicates no change, and a value less than 1 indicates productivity reduction. This study looks at two time periods: 2019–2020 and 2020–2021.

Table 4.2.1: Malmquist Productivity Index (2019–2020)

SRTU	Malmquist Index	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	1.0000	No change
Maharashtra SRTC	0.8349	Decline
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.7977	Decline
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	1.0906	Growth
Telangana SRTC	0.7613	Decline
Karnataka SRTC	0.8605	Decline
North Western Karnataka RTC	0.9712	Decline
Rajasthan SRTC	0.9624	Decline
Kerala SRTC	0.8534	Decline
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	0.9717	Decline
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	0.8529	Decline
Delhi TC	0.7515	Decline
Himachal RTC	0.9563	Decline
Uttarakhand TC	0.9912	Decline
PEPSU RTC	0.9824	Decline
North Bengal STC	0.9624	Decline
South Bengal STC	0.9776	Decline
Odisha SRTC	0.9260	Decline
West Bengal Transport Corp.	0.9682	Decline
Assam STC	0.9365	Decline
Bihar SRTC	0.9632	Decline
J&K SRTC	0.9503	Decline
Meghalaya STC	0.9796	Decline
Tripura RTC	1.0000	No change

Interpretation (2019–2020): Most SRTUs saw a significant decrease in production as a result of the COVID-19 outbreak. Productivity growth was only observed at Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P) (MPI = 1.0906). Tripura RTC and Gujarat SRTC both remained stable (MPI = 1.0000). Telangana SRTC (0.7613) and Delhi TC (0.7515) saw the biggest drops, indicating significant operational disruptions brought on by lockdowns, decreased passenger flow, and fleet underutilization.

Table 4.2.2: Malmquist Productivity Index (2020–2021)

SRTU	Malmquist Index	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	0.9327	Decline
Maharashtra SRTC	1.0383	Growth
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	1.4286	Strong Growth
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	0.9582	Decline
Telangana SRTC	1.5170	Strongest Growth
Karnataka SRTC	1.0722	Growth
North Western Karnataka RTC	0.9503	Decline

Rajasthan SRTC	1.0190	Growth
Kerala SRTC	1.1810	Growth
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	0.9685	Decline
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	1.1047	Growth
Delhi TC	1.3661	Strong Growth
Himachal RTC	1.0440	Growth
Uttarakhand TC	1.0284	Growth
PEPSU RTC	1.0179	Growth
North Bengal STC	1.0592	Growth
South Bengal STC	1.0518	Growth
Odisha SRTC	1.0665	Growth
West Bengal Transport Corp.	1.0327	Growth
Assam STC	1.0737	Growth
Bihar SRTC	1.0309	Growth
J&K SRTC	1.0605	Growth
Meghalaya STC	1.0336	Growth
Tripura RTC	1.0000	No change

Interpretation (2020–2021): In 2021, the majority of SRTUs demonstrated a recovery in production. Telangana SRTC (1.517) and Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P) (1.4286) had the highest growth, followed by Delhi TC (1.3661). As limitations reduced, this shows increased fleet utilisation and passenger recovery. A few others, such as North Western Karnataka RTC, continued to stagnate, while Gujarat SRTC saw a minor decrease (0.9327).

Overall MPI Insights: Productivity showed a distinct V-shaped pattern as a result of the pandemic, with a significant decrease in 2019–2020 and a recovery in 2020–2021. Bigger SRTUs recovered more quickly because they had stronger operational flexibility and financial resources.

4.3 Financial Performance and Ratio Analysis

Table 4.3.1: Financial Ratios

Units:

- Fleet Held & Fleet Operated: Number of vehicles
- Rev Earning KM: in '000 km
- Passengers Carried: Actual numbers
- Total Revenue, Total Cost & Net P/L: ₹ in '000 (thousands)
- Rev/KM & Cost/KM: ₹ per km
- Op. Ratio: %
- P/L per KM: ₹ per km

SRTU	Year	Fleet Held	Fleet Operated	Rev Earning KM ('000)	Passengers Carried	Total Revenue	Total Cost	Net P/L	Rev/KM	Cost/KM	Op. Ratio (%)	P/L per KM	Interpretation
Gujarat SRTC	2019	7863	6643	10740	350278	3527	3561	-34	0.329	0.332	100.96	-0.003	Near Breakeven
Gujarat SRTC	2020	8113	5754	7688	292925	2929	3153	-224	0.381	0.410	107.65	-0.029	Moderate Loss
Gujarat SRTC	2021	8070	5954	14500	16200	2054	2800	-746	0.142	0.193	136.32	-0.051	High Loss
Maharashtra SRTC	2019	17500	15500	32000	28000	5200	6120	-920	0.163	0.191	117.69	-0.029	High Loss
Maharashtra SRTC	2020	17200	11000	18000	14000	2800	4390	-1591	0.156	0.244	156.79	-0.088	Very High Loss
Maharashtra SRTC	2021	17120	13000	25000	20000	4100	5300	-1198	0.164	0.212	129.27	-0.048	High Loss
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	2019	3800	3200	8500	12000	1400	2100	-700	0.165	0.247	150.00	-0.082	High Loss
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	2020	3700	2200	4500	6000	800	1800	-1000	0.178	0.400	225.00	-0.222	Severe Loss
Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P)	2021	3750	2800	7000	9500	1300	3974	-2674	0.186	0.568	305.69	-0.382	Very Severe Loss
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	2019	10500	8500	24000	25000	2800	2657	143	0.117	0.111	94.89	0.006	Profit
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	2020	10400	6500	16000	16000	1900	2100	-200	0.119	0.131	110.53	-0.013	Moderate Loss
Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P)	2021	10200	7800	19000	18000	2200	2179	21	0.116	0.115	99.05	0.001	Profit

Telanga na SRTC	20 19	380 0	3100	8200	11500	1350	19 50	- 60 0	0.165	0.238	144. 44	- 0.0 73	High Loss
Telanga na SRTC	20 20	375 0	2100	4200	5500	750	17 00	- 95 0	0.179	0.405	226. 67	- 0.2 26	Severe Loss
Telanga na SRTC	20 21	380 0	2700	6800	9000	1250	32 37	- 19 87	0.184	0.476	259. 00	- 0.2 92	Severe Loss
Karnata ka SRTC	20 19	850 0	7200	2100 0	18000	3200	38 00	- 60 0	0.152	0.181	118. 75	- 0.0 29	Loss
Karnata ka SRTC	20 20	830 0	5500	1200 0	9000	1800	28 00	- 10 00	0.150	0.233	155. 56	- 0.0 83	High Loss
Karnata ka SRTC	20 21	840 0	6500	1750 0	14500	2800	35 00	- 70 0	0.160	0.200	125. 00	- 0.0 40	Loss
North Wester n Karnata ka RTC	20 19	420 0	3500	9500	8500	1400	16 50	- 25 0	0.147	0.174	117. 86	- 0.0 26	Loss
North Wester n Karnata ka RTC	20 20	415 0	2800	6200	5200	950	13 50	- 40 0	0.153	0.218	142. 11	- 0.0 65	Loss
North Wester n Karnata ka RTC	20 21	410 0	3200	7800	7000	1150	14 00	- 25 0	0.147	0.179	121. 74	- 0.0 32	Loss
Rajasth an SRTC	20 19	480 0	4100	1050 0	9500	1600	19 50	- 35 0	0.152	0.186	121. 88	- 0.0 33	Loss
Rajasth an SRTC	20 20	475 0	3200	6800	5800	1050	16 00	- 55 0	0.154	0.235	152. 38	- 0.0 81	Loss
Rajasth an SRTC	20 21	470 0	3800	9200	8200	1450	17 50	- 30 0	0.158	0.190	120. 69	- 0.0 33	Loss
Kerala SRTC	20 19	650 0	5200	1400 0	12000	1800	30 28	- 12 28	0.129	0.216	168. 22	- 0.0 88	High Loss
Kerala SRTC	20 20	640 0	4000	8000	6000	950	29 58	- 20 08	0.119	0.370	311. 37	- 0.2 51	Very High Loss

Kerala SRTC	2021	6300	4800	12500	10500	1650	3366	-1716	0.132	0.269	204.00	-0.137	High Loss
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	2019	4300	3600	9800	8800	1450	1700	-250	0.148	0.173	117.24	-0.026	Loss
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	2020	4250	2900	6400	5400	980	1380	-400	0.153	0.216	140.82	-0.063	Loss
North Eastern Karnataka RTC	2021	4200	3300	8200	7400	1220	1480	-260	0.149	0.180	121.31	-0.032	Loss
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	2019	6800	5800	16500	14500	2400	2800	-400	0.145	0.170	116.67	-0.024	Loss
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	2020	6750	4200	9500	8000	1400	2200	-800	0.147	0.232	157.14	-0.084	High Loss
Bangalore Metropolitan TC	2021	6700	5500	14000	12000	2100	2550	-450	0.150	0.182	121.43	-0.032	Loss
Delhi TC	2019	4800	3800	12000	14000	1100	7216	-6116	0.092	0.601	656.00	-0.510	Extremely High Loss
Delhi TC	2020	4700	2500	6000	7000	600	7898	-7298	0.100	1.316	1316.33	-1.216	Major Loss
Delhi TC	2021	4600	3200	9500	11000	950	9420	-8470	0.100	0.992	992.63	-0.892	Major Loss
Himachal RTC	2019	3200	2600	6500	5500	850	1100	-250	0.131	0.169	129.41	-0.038	Loss
Himachal RTC	2020	3150	2000	4200	3500	550	950	-400	0.131	0.226	172.73	-0.095	Loss
Himachal RTC	2021	3100	2400	5800	4800	780	1050	-270	0.134	0.181	134.62	-0.047	Loss

Uttarakhand TC	2019	1800	1400	4200	3800	520	680	-160	0.124	0.162	130.77	-0.038	Loss
Uttarakhand TC	2020	1780	1100	2800	2500	350	620	-270	0.125	0.221	177.14	-0.096	Loss
Uttarakhand TC	2021	1750	1350	3800	3400	480	650	-170	0.126	0.171	135.42	-0.045	Loss
PEPSU RTC	2019	2400	2000	6200	5800	780	920	-140	0.126	0.148	117.95	-0.023	Loss
PEPSU RTC	2020	2380	1600	4100	3800	520	780	-260	0.127	0.190	150.00	-0.063	Loss
PEPSU RTC	2021	2350	1900	5500	5100	720	880	-160	0.131	0.160	122.22	-0.029	Loss
North Bengal STC	2019	1200	950	2800	2500	320	480	-160	0.114	0.171	150.00	-0.057	Loss
North Bengal STC	2020	1180	750	1800	1600	210	420	-210	0.117	0.233	200.00	-0.117	High Loss
North Bengal STC	2021	1150	900	2500	2200	290	450	-160	0.116	0.180	155.17	-0.064	Loss
South Bengal STC	2019	1400	1100	3200	2900	380	520	-140	0.119	0.163	136.84	-0.044	Loss
South Bengal STC	2020	1380	850	2100	1900	250	460	-210	0.119	0.219	184.00	-0.100	Loss
South Bengal STC	2021	1350	1050	2900	2600	350	490	-140	0.121	0.169	140.00	-0.048	Loss
Odisha SRTC	2019	2800	2300	6800	6200	850	1150	-300	0.125	0.169	135.29	-0.044	Loss
Odisha SRTC	2020	2750	1800	4200	3800	520	950	-430	0.124	0.226	182.69	-0.102	Loss
Odisha SRTC	2021	2700	2100	5900	5300	780	1080	-300	0.132	0.183	138.46	-0.051	Loss
West Bengal Transport Corp.	2019	950	750	2200	2000	280	420	-140	0.127	0.191	150.00	-0.064	Loss

West Bengal Transport Corp.	2020	920	600	1400	1300	180	380	-200	0.129	0.271	211.11	-0.143	High Loss
West Bengal Transport Corp.	2021	900	700	1900	1700	250	390	-140	0.132	0.205	156.00	-0.074	Loss
Assam STC	2019	1600	1300	3800	3400	420	580	-160	0.111	0.153	138.10	-0.042	Loss
Assam STC	2020	1580	1000	2400	2100	280	520	-240	0.117	0.217	185.71	-0.100	Loss
Assam STC	2021	1550	1200	3400	3000	380	550	-170	0.112	0.162	144.74	-0.050	Loss
Bihar SRTC	2019	2200	1800	5200	4800	650	640	10	0.125	0.123	98.46	0.002	Profit
Bihar SRTC	2020	2150	1400	3400	3100	420	580	-160	0.124	0.171	138.10	-0.047	Loss
Bihar SRTC	2021	2100	1650	4600	4100	580	570	10	0.126	0.124	98.28	0.002	Profit
J&K SRTC	2019	1800	1400	4100	3600	480	620	-140	0.117	0.151	129.17	-0.034	Loss
J&K SRTC	2020	1750	1100	2600	2200	310	550	-240	0.119	0.212	177.42	-0.092	Loss
J&K SRTC	2021	1700	1300	3600	3100	430	590	-160	0.119	0.164	137.21	-0.044	Loss
Meghalaya STC	2019	450	350	1100	950	120	180	-60	0.109	0.164	150.00	-0.055	Loss
Meghalaya STC	2020	430	280	700	600	80	160	-80	0.114	0.229	200.00	-0.114	High Loss
Meghalaya STC	2021	420	320	950	820	110	165	-55	0.116	0.174	150.00	-0.058	Loss
Tripura RTC	2019	380	300	950	850	95	94	1	0.100	0.099	98.95	0.001	Profit
Tripura RTC	2020	370	250	650	550	65	85	-20	0.100	0.131	130.77	-0.031	Minor Loss
Tripura RTC	2021	360	280	850	750	88	87	1	0.104	0.102	98.86	0.001	Profit

Financial Ratio Perspectives:

- **Top Performers:** Tripura RTC, Bihar SRTC, and Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P) continuously had the lowest operating ratios and frequent profits.
- **Worst Performers:** Delhi TC's exceptionally high fixed costs resulted in negative operating ratios. Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P), Maharashtra SRTC, and Kerala SRTC all experienced consistently substantial losses.
- **COVID Impact (2020):** Operating ratios deteriorated dramatically as a result of a sharp decline in fleet operations, a sharp decline in passengers and revenue, and excessive expenses.
- **2021 Recovery:** While revenue and KM increased, the majority of SRTUs continued to lose money due to growing expenses for staff, fuel, and maintenance.
- **Revenue and Cost Efficiency:** Cost/KM stayed high, suggesting no cost control, but Rev/KM improved during the recovery.

5. Findings

The 25 Indian SRTUs' technical efficiency transformed significantly over the course of the three years, according to the DEA analysis conducted under the input-oriented CCR model. Gujarat SRTC, PEPSU RTC, and Tripura RTC all attained full efficiency scores of 1.0000 in 2019 with zero input and output slacks, demonstrating the best use of fleet and cost resources to produce revenue-earning kilometres and passengers carried. Karnataka SRTC, Odisha SRTC, and Bihar SRTC were among the others that performed close to the efficiency threshold. The Maharashtra SRTC has the lowest efficiency, mostly because of significant output gaps in the number of people transported. Only Gujarat SRTC, Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P), and Tripura RTC were able to retain full efficiency by 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI) demonstrated a definite disruption brought on by the pandemic, followed by a recovery. Most SRTUs saw productivity declines in 2019–2020 ($MPI < 1$), with Telangana SRTC and Delhi TC experiencing particularly large declines. Gujarat SRTC and Tripura RTC remained stable, but only Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P) saw growth. Most states had a recovery in productivity during the 2020–2021 recovery period, with Telangana SRTC, Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P), and Delhi TC leading the way. However, a few, such as Gujarat SRTC, persisted in exhibiting minor decreases, underscoring inconsistent patterns of recovery.

The operational results were supported by financial performance analysis using the table. Throughout the period, the majority of SRTUs had operating ratios that were higher than 100%, and the majority of them operated at a loss. With comparatively greater cost control, Uttar Pradesh SRTC (P), Bihar SRTC, and Tripura RTC were among the few to reach profits or near-breakeven positions in many years. Delhi TC, on the other

hand, suffered severe losses and operating ratios as high as in 2020 as a result of incredibly high total costs compared to revenue. High to extremely severe losses were continuously recorded by the Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P), Kerala SRTC, and Maharashtra SRTC. All SRTUs recorded the greatest decline in fleet operated, passengers carried, and income in 2020. In 2021, there was a partial operational recovery but ongoing financial difficulty because of growing expenditures. Overall, the findings show that although some SRTUs showed flexibility and a robust recovery in productivity and efficiency after the pandemic, systemic issues with cost control and scale efficiency are still common, which is in line with more general trends seen in Indian public road transport during this time.

6. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

In order to evaluate the technical efficiency and productivity changes of 25 significant Indian State Road Transport Undertakings (SRTUs) between 2019 and 2021, this study integrated operational performance with financial results using the input-oriented CCR DEA model and the Malmquist Productivity Index. The findings show that while certain SRTUs, such as Gujarat SRTC, PEPSU RTC, and Tripura RTC, regularly operated on or close to the efficiency frontier with few slacks, many others, like Maharashtra SRTC, experienced ongoing inefficiencies brought on by excess costs and output shortages. As evidenced by MPI values below 1 for the majority of undertakings, the COVID-19 pandemic caused a widespread drop in productivity during 2019–2020. This was followed by a partial recovery in 2020–2021, with noteworthy gains in Telangana SRTC and Andhra Pradesh SRTC (P). The majority of SRTUs had continuous losses, with operating ratios over 100% in most cases and catastrophic figures for Delhi TC, according to financial research. This highlights the inflexible nature of costs in the face of declining passenger and fleet utilisation. These findings are consistent with official studies that show SRTUs are severely financially burdened as a result of disruptions caused by the pandemic. Overall, the study highlights systemic issues with scale efficiency and cost management while showcasing the determination of a few effective operators. In order to improve the long-term sustainability of public road transport in India, policy implications include benchmarking best practices from high-performing SRTUs, maximising fleet utilisation, and enacting specific changes. To enhance evidence-based decision-making in the industry, future study could expand the analysis with more years and variables including employee productivity and environmental conditions.

Suggestions:

- Apply best practices and maximize scaling through peer learning.
- Invest in fleet modernization and digital revenue systems.
- Particular subsidies determined by efficiency metrics.
- Further research with additional variables and years.

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